

Nature Writing and Conservation with Special Reference to Romantic Poetry: A Study

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Abstract:

Literature can raise awareness, inspire action and foster a deeper connection to nature, which can all contribute to solving environmental issues. Nature writing as a genre, primarily focusses on the relationship between human beings and the natural world and studied with an acute awareness of the environmental degradation being wrought on the nature by human intervention. By studying the interplay between nature writing and environmental conservation, this research paper carefully examines the power of narrative in environmental advocacy and offers insights into effective ways for promoting sustainability through literature. Wordsworth's philosophy of pantheism could provide a direction and path in developing a positive attitude towards all aspects of nature. Like Wordsworth, Ruskin too experiences a communion with nature. Due to industrialisation, existing harmony between human and nature is disturbed. So, poets preferred to go back to the natural surroundings in the tranquil and harmonious environment. This study endeavours to illustrate the symbiotic relationship between literature and nature by dissecting literary narratives with environmental implications.

Key Words: Literature, Nature, Communion, Industrialisation, Harmonious, Environment.

Introduction:

Literature can raise awareness, inspire action and foster a deeper connection to nature, which can all contribute to solving environmental issues. Poems can convey the beauty of the natural world, highlight environmental challenges, and evoke empathy and a sense of responsibility towards the planet. Additionally, poets can use their craft to advocate for sustainable practices, conservation efforts, and environmental justice, encouraging individuals and communities to take meaningful action to protect the environment.

There is a need to create environmental awareness among the people. It is necessary to nurture the importance of environment in the minds of the people. As human beings, we have the responsibility to take the stewardship of the earth and its resources. We should not engage in exploitation of natural resources. This shows that human beings should exercise restraint in the use of natural resources. Such thinking is now increasingly becoming mainstream with greater knowledge and awareness of environmental problems. Wordsworth does not recognize separate rules for separate elements of life, but saw all these elements in an integrated manner. This shows the best ecological visionary approach towards nature. It is for this reasons that Wordsworth is acknowledged all over the world over as an ecologist with a foresight.

Nature writing as a genre, primarily focusses on the relationship between human beings and the natural world and studied with an acute awareness of the environmental degradation being wrought on the nature by human intervention. It has been long-standing wisdom started from the transcendental insights of Henry David Thoreau to the poignant environmental activism in Rachel Carson's works. In short, it has shown mirror to the society and influenced minds of the readers toward conservation and environmental stewardship.

Significance of the Study:

Slowly and gradually, we could trace that man's greed exceeded over his needs. He became so selfish and ceased his thinking prowess for the environment. Human beings are the members of the environment and should contribute in its development of life and not interfere and exploit its natural resources. By studying the interplay between nature writing and environmental conservation, this research paper carefully examines the power of narrative in environmental advocacy and offers insights into effective ways for promoting sustainability through literature.

Objectives:

The research work attempts

1. To create awareness about the relationship between human activities and the natural world.
2. To analyze the concern for environmental issues through the study of nature writing.
3. To explore and inculcate the values for sustainable and holistic way of living.

Hypothesis:

Natural study celebrates the beauty and spiritual values of the natural world. Nature is the cure for human beings. All nature study reveals that unprecedented growth in environmental problems and teaches us to love nature in order to conserve all aspects of the natural world.

Methodology:

Data Collection: Primary Sources: Key nature writing texts from different periods and regions.

Secondary Sources: Scholarly articles, critiques, and historical documents related to conservation movements.

Literature Review:

Ruskin is too impressed with picturesque natural scenery of the nature. His natural human instincts like feeling, seeing, responding, loving and caring are developed in the company of mountains. Wordsworth has greatly influenced John Ruskin in his adolescent period. Like Wordsworth, he too experiences a communion with nature. Like Wordsworth, he too believed that presence of beauty of nature in the universe led to presence of God. He too reinforces his belief that the writer or poet should find out beauty even in trivial or contemptible things of nature. He finds a moral and social messages in the first sights of Alps.

Following views validates the above discussion.

“ Ruskin was deeply eco-conscious, the first major British writer to record a sense that nature's powers of recovery might not be infinite, and the modern form of production and consumption have the potential to inflict fatal environmental damage : in his lecture on what he called ‘ the storm cloud of the nineteenth century’ which he also called ‘the modern plague-cloud’, he expressed his deep anxiety that the atmosphere was being permanently damaged by industrial pollution, which might say was the environmental consequences of assuming that our ‘dominion’ over nature need have no limits The ‘minatory’ Ruskin is convinced, after twenty years of making observations, that cloud formations, atmospheric

conditions, and weather patterns had changed during that time.” (Beginning theory: An introduction to literary and cultural theory: By Peter Barry)

Almost all Romantic poets find that the root cause of environmental degradation lies in its separation or alienation of human beings from their organic unity with nature. Their literary work, particularly poetry shows concern for changing cultural views for nature. The simple solution of this malady lies in a reunion between human beings and nature. Let's consider Wordsworth's view towards nature. He based his theory of nature on the concept of pantheism which underlies the facts that all natural objects are intrinsically signs of a larger part of Divine Design. Nature is nothing but a temple of learning. Wordsworth aims at raising ecological consciousness.

Discussion;

Wordsworth's philosophy of pantheism could provide a direction and path in developing a positive attitude towards all aspects of nature. Close reading of his nature poetry could nurture harmony between humanity and nature. Wordsworth admires the beauty and grandeur of nature and also the God's mighty power and artistic skills in managing all the aspects of nature. In society there are those individuals who have an intense connection with nature. William Wordsworth is a romanticist, pantheist and transcendentalist. His belief system is based on the fact that the natural world is an emblem of God or the Divine. His poetry often celebrates the beauty and spiritual values of the natural world. It shows that nature as cure for all humanity, the cure for all deeds and a guide to them all. Man's origins lie in nature, it is where man begins and where man ends. Close reading of his nature poetry could nurture harmony between humanity and nature. Wordsworth admires the beauty and grandeur of nature and also the God's mighty power and artistic skills in managing all the aspects of nature.

Nature represents only the Ultimate with the invisible laws, the reality of unseen. Wordsworth takes shelter with nature, with the ultimate laws. Thus, nature is the ultimate device of God. Great things happen not by enforcement. What we see today is vast collective money mindedness. Money is there, but there is no contentment. Life has gone down the drain. Thereby, man becomes most discontented. Everything here is bound to fail if it is not wedded with the world. If the cherished goal is not found in the miserable world, then try for the natural world. We would not be disappointed. Contentment and peacefulness are the qualities of the centre and not of the circumference. But modern man is deeply frustrated, as he

remains aloof from nature. Intellectually he is right, but intuitively, he is wrong. He failed to understand that more and more expectations from material world brings more and more frustrations. He feels boredom, rightly so, because boredom too teaches him that life is meaningless. That's why Wordsworth is hurt to see humanity at loss because it has disobeyed the natural laws of the world. This is not a new situation, this has been always there, since there is a subtle desire of humanity to dominate nature. That's why, through Wordsworth opens his heart and share new insights of pantheism, if we listen and learn something out of it, it will open up new vistas of understanding and love about nature.

Due to industrialisation, existing harmony between human and nature is disturbed. So, poets preferred to go back to the natural surroundings in the tranquil and harmonious environment. Romantic poets had tried to present ecological viewpoints in order to highlight major problems like shortages of natural resources and environmental crisis. They fundamentally stressed on how ecological crisis is a threat to the very existence of human beings. Keats, like Mahatma Gandhi, preferred going back to the elemental simplicities of village life to find solace and comfort for his soul. His disenchantment for the city- life, is quite perceptible in the following lines:

“To one who has been long in city pent,
'Tis very sweet to look into the fair
And open face of heaven, —to breathe a prayer
Full in the smile of the blue firmament.
Who is happier, when, with heart's content,
Fatigued he sinks into some pleasant lair
Of wavy grass, and reads a debonair
And gentle tale of love and languishment?
Returning home at evening, with an ear
Catching the notes of Philomel, —an eye
Watching the sailing cloudlet's bright career,
He mourns that day so soon has glided by:
E'en like the passage of an angel's tear
That falls through the clear ether silently.” (To One Who Has Been Long in City Pent by
John Keats)

Since Keats is born and brought up city life of London, he is fed up with city life. He has a longing for village life. Man in the city is like a caged bird. Monotony of city life has cramped his creativity. Simple village life, where air is unpolluted, clear unclouded sky, sweet aroma of soil, the sights and sounds of nature, has fascinated Keats's mind. Healthy, happy and contented life can be found only in the villages. He finds the surrounding extremely pleasant, "to look into the fair and open face of heaven" In city, our vision is blocked by tall towers, dust and smoke, we are not able to see clear blue sky. His short visit to the beautiful and enchanting village landscape made him to extol the virtues of simple village life.

Thoreau too not only found in nature beauty, comfort and solace, but he also found spiritualization of human life. As naturalist, he was also a creative thinker. An ascetic with a passion for living. He is self-taught naturalist. He announced his own independence from society on July 4, 1845, by shifting into his pond-side hut. He was a free soul. He had a passion for natural life. He is an ideal man. An ideal man is non-attached. He is not attached to his bodily pleasures and sensations. He did not have craving for power and possessions. Thus, the pond, the dawn, the change of seasons, the sun's warmth and light are symbols of self-realization. He lived his life as simple as possible. He communicated to the reader symbolic relation between nature and spirit. He simplified his material wants. He satisfied his thirst by the bounty of the woods and lake. In *Walden* (1854), he escaped himself from material life to a life of solitude and self-reliance at Walden Pond. His withdrawal from mundane life to the life that is close to elemental rhythms of nature like Lord Buddha's withdrawal from life to gain enlightenment. Thoreau, in the company of nature gets a new insight on the universal problems of mundane world. Wordsworth shows ecological perspective through nature poetry and enlightens people on the issues of ecological crisis.

Romanticism is to be regarded as ecological and mechanical in depiction of the universe. Wordsworth's poetry appeals readers to look at nature from a holistic point of view. It is an ecological commitment towards nature. He subsumes his nature poetry into a broad perspective of ecological vision. Wordsworth himself has proclaimed that a poet must amuse as well as instruct. The purpose of poetry is didactic and instructive. His is a comprehensive approach towards poetry. Man's changing attitude towards nature from cooperation to antagonism and his consequent alienation from nature has led him to think seriously about nature. Intellectual as well as artistic elements of the Romantic era are meant for a reaction against the scientific and rationalistic ideology of the enlightenment. In the late eighteenth

century, vast expanding industrialisation and corresponding materialism have led to spiritual alienation of the people from the nature. Nature too has to looked down upon as commodity. Degradation of nature and degradation of humans took place simultaneously. Therefore, there was a call for “back to nature”. Wordsworth, Keats and Shelley had expressed apprehensions for newly developed railways at the cost of spoliation of pure and beautiful landscape of the Lake District. These undesirable and harmful changes due to development of technology has posed serious threats for the conservation pure natural landscape. Wordsworth as an icon of Romantic poetry expressed his reservations over the railway network extensions and corresponding alienation of urban population of industrial cities from nature. Modern man too wants to be a conqueror of nature. Almost all the writers of Romantic era look at nature with religious point of view. One of the reasons for development of special bond with nature is Industrial Revolution which compelled people to leave their native rural landscape and migrate to cities. Poet like Shelley believed in nature as a source of healthy emotions. Henry David Thoreau recommended people to live in the company of nature rather than living in polluted unhealthy cities. It will aid man to connect with his true self, which will not be found in crowded cities. We are alone even if we are with the crowd in cities. So much so that, romantic poets elevated the nature to a spiritual level. They emphasised on the oneness of nature and humanity. Humanity and nature don't have a separate existence. Romantic poet like Wordsworth exults the virtue of simple, pure and peerless natural village life. He also contrasts the urban and rural life. The company of nature gives serenity and joy of heaven. He captures the beautiful moments of rural folks when they roam and breathes a pure air free from dust, dirt and smoke and he is happy in the company of nature.

Conclusion: This research paper illustrates the close affinity between nature writing and conservation of environment. It underlines literary narratives and their impact on human consciousness. It also emphasises on the enduring influence of literature in promoting a sustainable and conscientious association with nature. This study endeavours to illustrate the symbiotic relationship between literature and nature by dissecting literary narratives with environmental implications. This research paper explores the role of nature writing in shaping and promoting environmental conservation. It seeks to understand how literary works contribute to environmental awareness, influence public opinion, and inspire policy changes related to conservation.

Scope for further Study:

It can be further explored as how modern and postmodern literature analyses the process of urbanisation and industrialisation and their impact on the environment. How urban spaces show human disconnection from nature.

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